

Calculating the dispersion factor and the efficiency of solar cells based on their packages

Wahidullah Enayat^{1*}, Khujasta Nazari¹, Ahmad Shorab Zaki¹, Mujibullah Mahboob²

¹ Department of Physics, Education Faculty, Samangan Higher Education Institute, Samangan, Afghanistan

² Department of Physics, Education Faculty, Balkh University, Balkh, Afghanistan

Abstract

Solar cells can be used to build large assemblies of solar panels. In this paper, the calculation of a dispersion factor and the efficiency of the solar cell is done by two methods, one is parallel, and the other is series. The results of parallel and series method packing show that the output power is the same in both methods and the current or voltage will be variable. For higher voltages is series panels and for higher currents is parallel panels. Or even it can be used combination of parallel and in series panels. The data also shows that in parallel mode has more current with dispersion factor (0.37%) and efficiency of solar cells (0.03%). In series mode, has more voltage with dispersion factor (0.63%) and efficiency of solar cells (0.12%) is obtained.

Keywords: solar cell, solar panels, dispersion factor, cell efficiency, series and parallel.

1.Introduction

The sun is one of the largest sources of energy in the world[1].It is composed of hydrogen gases (73.46%), helium (24.85%) and other elements [2].It is more than 14 billion years old and will be a huge source of energy for the next 5 billion years [3]. The temperature in the center is about 20 million degrees Kelvin and its surface is equivalent to 6000 degrees Kelvin [4].Sunlight covers the UV to infrared range [5].About 40% of this energy is in the visible range and about 50% is in the infrared range [6].Photons in the ultraviolet and visible range provide the energy needed to excite electrons in semiconductor materials.This phenomenon is effectively used in the production of electric current.It usually produces solar cells from the composition and thin film of semiconductors. A solar cell comprises a junction of p-type and n-type semiconductors [7].Today, the use of new energy sources, especially solar energy, has received a great deal of attention from scientists due to its high capacity, easy access, and low cost. Therefore, understanding the methods of converting solar energy into electrical energy has a great impact on the development of the use of this energy [8],[9].Solar cells include pigment-sensitive solar cells and polymer solar cells. The main components of solar cells are light-absorbing or electron-hole-producing compounds [10]. In dye-sensitized solar cells, the dye is responsible for absorbing light and transferring electrons to the semiconductor [11].

Therefore, understanding the structure and function of the dye in a dye-sensitized solar cell is of particular importance [12]. For this reason, the introduction of dyes, performance mechanisms, and current developments related to their application in dyes sensitive to solar cells had been presented [11]. Also, using black pomegranate skin pigment a sensitizer and nanofibers, and the combination of nanoparticles and nanofibers as a pigment substrate in a pigment substrate in a pigment-sensitive solar cell, the extent of cell function improvement was investigated [11]. Black pomegranate skin pigment had good absorption on the nanostructure due to its carbonyl and carboxyl functional groups [11]. On the other hand, black pomegranate skin pigment with a wide range of light absorption spectrum improved solar cell efficiency [13]. These cases were investigated for pigments using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and ultraviolet–visible spectrophotometry (UV-Vis analyzes) [14].

Fig.1.Extraction of black pomegranate skin pigment-containing anthocyanin's (collection of black pomegranate), b) separation of black skin, c) dried skin powder and) d extraction of pigment [13].

In the nanostructure part, with the change of nanoparticles to nano fibers and finally, the combined use of nano fibers and TiO₂ nanoparticles, an acceptable increase in efficiency was observed [12]. The best performance in the cell made of nan fibers was 20% nanoparticles with an efficiency of 2.82%, a charge factor of 79.6%, a short-circuit current density of 2.18 mA, and an open-circuit voltage of 5,032 V. For other cells made with Nanoparticles, nan fibers, nan fiber composition, and 30% nanoparticles and nan fiber composition and 40% nanoparticles, yields of 1.77, 1.84, 0.64 and 0.61% were obtained, respectively [13]. Dye Sensitized Solar Cell (DSSC) among the solar cell generations, due to their simple structure, low price, ability to generate electricity in cloudy air and under artificial light, as well as environmental compatibility are of interest to researchers [12]. The DSSC is a semiconductor device based on the conversion of solar radiation into electrical energy (Fig.2) [11].

Fig.2. Structure and working process of DSSC solar cell[13].

Transparent Conducting Oxide (TCO), usually from Fluorine doped Tin Oxide (FTO) or Indium doped Tin Oxide (ITO) [16]. The porous layer of metal oxide that is used as a photoanode (usually titanium dioxide (TiO_2) nanoparticles in the solar cell [13]. Sensitizers (pigment molecules) that are adsorbed on the photoanode [17]. Electrolyte, mostly iodide-triiodide electrolyte, which plays the role of open conversion [10]. In pigment-sensitive cells, the pigment molecules that are adsorbed on the surface of the porous TiO_2 layer absorb and excite the colliding photons [12].

Activated solar cells are pigments of the third generation of solar cells. These cells were first built with high efficiency in 1991[15]. Although these cells are less efficient than traditional silicon cells, they cost less energy to be made [2]. In order to make this type of solar cell, a nanoporous layer with a micrometer thickness of titanium dioxide is needed [13]. Electrophoretic deposition of nanoparticles from the suspension is an effective and inexpensive way to create this capability [16]. Of course, the layer cracks at thicknesses higher than 1 micrometer, and in this article, we examine the process of producing a multi-micrometer layer without cracking and compare the efficiency of the cell made with crack and without cracking [10]. The multi-stage coating of nanoparticles in the suspension can eliminate the presence of cracks even at a thickness of more than $2 \mu\text{m}$. At first, the thin layers of titanium dioxide produced after activation were placed by N719 dye and analyzed at IV photoelectrode site and the improvement of cell properties was proved as a result of the multi-stage coating [17].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Methods

To characterize the solar cell, used light intensity with an average intensity of $100 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$ which resulted in a current-voltage (I-V) graph, open-circuit voltage loss ($V_{oc} - T$), short-circuit current loss ($I_{sc} - T$) are obtained

[14]. Power efficiency is obtained by characterizing the current-voltage graph. In this measurement, the cell is irradiated in reverse bias and a scan of the voltage and photovoltaic produced is recorded [10]. Short-circuit current, open voltage, dispersion factor ff , cell efficiency, photovoltaic parameters can be measured by Eg.1 and 2[8].

$$\eta = \frac{I_{sc}V_{oc}}{P_{incident}} ff \quad (1)$$

$$ff = \frac{I_m V_m}{I_{sc} V_{oc}}$$

$$\eta = \frac{I_m V_m}{P_{incident}} \quad (2)$$

in the above equation η is cell efficiency, I_{sc} is short current, V_{oc} is open circuit voltage, ff is dispersion factor and $P_{incident}$ is incidence light density [7]. In Eq.1, we add the quantity of the dispersion factor which results in Eq.2. In Eq.2, I_m is the maximum current and V_m is the maximum voltage. The dispersion factor is a measure of a square of a curve and a value between 0 and 1[6].

2.2 Experiment:

The experiment is performed by connecting the device to one of the solar cells and turning on the spotlight so that it is at a distance of 15 cm from the solar cell. At this distance from the source is about one-sixth the power of the sun. Turn on the computer and run the I-V program. Selected for current 10 mA and for voltage 2 mV. Now click on the start button and wait for the current-voltage graph of the solar cell. We perform this experiment for Sample 1 (single cells) and Sample 2 (even cells) that are packed in parallel and in series Table 1. To use cells in electrical circuits, we need to have the voltage-current electrical characteristic of a solar cell.

3. Results and Discussion

This electrical characteristic depends on the intensity of the light emitted, and its characteristic curve changes depending on the intensity of the light, and this change is in a way that increases the short-circuit current. The voltage that a cell produces against light intensity is about half a volt, and its short-circuit current can vary from a mill ampere to several amps. The maximum output power of a cell is equal to the product of the open circuit voltage multiplied by the short circuit current, which is used to determine the output power of the cell. So the output power of a cell will vary from a few mill watts to a few watts.

One of the factors that affect the cell production capacity is the size of the cell surface, and the larger the cell area, the greater the production capacity. In addition to the surface, the output power also depends on the light intensity, and as the light intensity increases, the output power increases. The temperature of the cell reduces the voltage

across the diode bond of the cell and reduces the output power, but its effect is not severe and is sometimes negligible.

Table 1: dispersion factor and the efficiency of solar cells based on their packages.

Materials	$I_{sc}(mA)$	$V_{oc}(v)$	$I_m(mA)$	$V_m(v)$	$P_{incident}$	ff	η
Sample 1 (single cell)	1.73	1.8	1.67	1.41	100	0.73	%0.023
Sample 2 (even cell)	2	1.6	1.9	1.11	100	0.65	%0.025
Series	3	5.4	2.5	4	100	0.63	%0.12
Parallel	4	2	3	1.2	100	0.37	%0.03

From Table (1), $I_{sc}(mA)$ is short current mille ampere, $V_{oc}(v)$ is open circuit voltage, $P_{incident}$ is incidence light density, ff is dispersion factor and η is cell efficiency. We conclude that both series and parallel methods can be used, because the output power is the same in both methods, but the current or voltage will be variable, so according to the need, for high voltage panels should be connected in series and for more current panels should be connected parallel, or even combined. According to the Table 1, in the series mode the voltage and in the parallel mode the current increases compared to the state of a cell. The data also shows that in a parallel mode more current with dispersion factor (0.37%) and efficiency of solar cells (0.03%) and in a series mode, more voltage with dispersion factor (0.63%) and efficiency of solar cells (0.12%) is obtained.

3. Conclusion:

In the construction of large sets of solar panels, both series and parallel methods are used simultaneously, the output power is the same in both methods and the current or voltage will be variable. The data also show that in a parallel mode more current with dispersion factor (0.37%) and efficiency of solar cells (0.03%) and in a series mode, more voltage with dispersion factor (0.63%) and efficiency of solar cells (0.12%) is obtained. For higher voltage, the panels can be series and for higher current, the panels can be parallel. Or even combined for some panels, meaning they were used both in parallel and in series.

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